

**IMPROVEMENT OF PEDAGOGICAL MECHANISMS OF
PROFESSIONAL AND PRACTICAL TRAINING OF STUDENTS OF
PHYSICAL CULTURE (IN THE EXAMPLE OF PHYSICAL CULTURE
EDUCATION)**

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Abstract. In our country, special attention is paid to raising a generation that is physically and mentally healthy, no less than others. After all, bringing up a highly moral, all-around perfect generation is an important factor in securing the future of our country and realizing all our noble goals. Extensive work is being done for this noble goal. Consistent reforms in areas such as protection of family, motherhood and childhood, development of children's sports, and improvement of the education system are bearing great results. Improvement of pedagogical mechanisms of professional and practical training of students of physical culture (in the example of physical culture education) is detailed in this article.

Key words: physical culture, pedagogical skill, Ministry of Health, spiritual maturity, public health, etc.

The independence and prospects of our country require ensuring the prospects of our great future. It is one of the most urgent tasks of our society to protect the health of the population, to always ensure their physical and spiritual well-being. On this basis, life itself proves that the purposeful use of all medical and physical culture activities related to health care in the family, school, and especially in the neighborhood and labor communities is a priority. Currently, the requirements of the special test "Alpomish and Barchinoy" are being used. The training of mature specialists is well underway by gradually increasing the physical fitness of

growing students, attracting talented young people to sports and improving their skills. In this area, the laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On physical training and sports", "On tourism" and the measures of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "Measures for the further development of physical training and sports in Uzbekistan" are relevant. "About", "On the organization of activities of the Children's Sports Development Fund of Uzbekistan", "On the measures for the further development of mass sports promotion" are important. It is worth noting that in the government's decisions, the development of student sports of vocational colleges, sports organizations of the republic and regions, public education and higher and secondary special educational institutions "Umid Nihollar", "Barkamol Avlod" and "Universiada" or three-stage sports competitions are held regularly. At the core of the competitions, the goal-oriented use of physical education and sports is embodied in improving the physical fitness of young students, training them to be capable of labor and defense work, and forming the most important healthy lifestyle skills. Practical and creative activities of physical education teachers and sports coaches are highly prioritized in educating young people in general and special physical training, in improving sports skills of talented young people. One of their exemplary services is that it serves to a certain extent in guiding the students to the profession (educational, cultural, medical, industrial construction, production, etc.) and arming them with practical special physical training.

Through physical training and sports, future specialists are constantly trained to increase production productivity, improve labor skills, live a long life, inculcate a healthy lifestyle, and acquire theoretical and practical skills. In the short time since our independence, the methods, forms and content of physical education and sports training in our Republic have been radically changed. Improving educational strategies and mechanisms for physical education in the world education system based on the principles of modern development, training

creative thinking personnel, introducing pedagogical innovations in accordance with development trends and improving them based on evaluation of their effectiveness, training competitive personnel is one of the current problems is considered In the process of educating the young generation, who are the future of our country, taking into account the incomparable nature of physical education, sports and national folk games, educating the young generation into physically fit and intellectually mature people is one of the urgent tasks of all pedagogical teams together with physical education and sports specialists. It is aimed at raising the knowledge and skills of young specialists to the level of modern requirements, improving the quality of education and training processes conducted with young people in the formation of students as mature specialists, and improving the educational effect. The historical situation in the development of society created clear opportunities for the public to participate in the management of physical education and sports, which helped to develop a form of independent management in the management of the physical education movement. In this way, a public form of management appears, which is important even today. The organization of work in the form of physical education and sports community is described in this way, it is carried out on the basis of the electability, independent activity and voluntariness of the leading bodies, which in turn helps to develop creative initiative. Activities of public physical education organizations are directly managed by trade unions and other community organizations. The functions of forms of independence are wide and comprehensive. This is to ensure the development and improvement of sports at a high level, the training of highly qualified athletes, the proper organization of work and recreation, strengthening health and maintaining creative longevity, attracting young people to sports and physical education of the population of different ages.

Educational activities, educational and sports activities in educational institutions are conducted on the basis of model programs and regulations that

have the nature of recommendation. Their activities are organized on the basis of democracy, initiative and broad involvement of the public. Republican Federations and relevant local organizations were established in order to establish relations with international Federations and to manage it. Sports Federations are public bodies, provide assistance to departments, departments and other divisions in the development of relevant sports, and also direct the activities of regional sports federations and sections and offices of sports societies. The physical education activities organized in educational institutions are as follows: Morning gymnastics held before the training sessions are physical exercises that are held every day before the start of classes in educational institutions. Pre-workout gymnastics mainly solves educational and fitness issues. Exercises held in the open factory also help to train the student body. Breaks should be used so that students can relax and prepare for the next lesson very effectively. The following requirements are imposed on the organization of various sports events and activities during recess games in educational institutions: They should be suitable for the age characteristics of children and should not tire them too much and should not be too exciting. use has a positive effect on the development of students. One of the extracurricular activities in educational institutions is mass physical culture and sports. The tasks of extracurricular work are as follows: Helping students to strengthen their health, to train their bodies, and to help them in their all-round physical development; Deepening and expanding the knowledge, skills and abilities of students acquired in physical culture classes; Organizing students to have a good rest; from the various forms of organizing and conducting educational and training sessions for various types of sports in order to arouse enthusiasm for physical education and sports in students and to form their movement skills, to involve students in extracurricular activities should be used. Their age, health and physical fitness are taken into account. Circles are formed to conduct practical work with students.

In addition to physical training educational institutions, students and teenagers study and practice sports in sports educational institutions, Olympic Reserve Sports College, sports educational institutions, and educational institutions for the improvement of sports skills. classes are included. In these institutions, students undergo special training in sports. They specialize in sports and qualify for high-level sports competitions. Also, activities outside of educational institutions from physical education include various sports competitions between educational institutions and competitions on holidays, friendly meetings. Conducting physical education activities in the residences and in the family is also the task of this field, and as a result, they form different, difficult and easy movements and skills. The rector of educational institutions, deputy rector for educational affairs and the head of the team of physical education of educational institutions are in charge of activities related to physical education. They are obliged to organize and monitor and encourage each student to engage in physical education and sports, and to take them under medical supervision. The following requirements are followed in the training of physical education specialists. Currently, the issue of providing highly qualified and knowledgeable specialists to the national economy of our country is being solved in the higher education system. Good experiences have been gained in planning the training of specialists in this field, and now the provision of science, culture and art specialists in all sectors of the economy is planned.

The results of the pedagogical process in physical education depend on the quality of the educational and educational work carried out in the classes. This can be achieved only by solving the tasks in the content of each lesson. Physical education classes have the functions of education, upbringing and health. Educational tasks include children's knowledge of physical culture and sports, health care, daily routine, proper breathing, exercise, and proper exercise. There may be special lessons dedicated to solving educational tasks. The teacher

complicates the exercises or complicates the conditions for performing them, and creates some difficulties in order to educate children's perseverance and ability to overcome difficulties. Rehabilitation tasks should be solved in every lesson, as well as educational tasks. Proper organization and conduct of physical culture classes, training in appropriate clothes, maintenance of necessary sanitary and hygienic conditions at the training place, holding classes in the open air - all this creates favorable conditions for solving health problems. One of the most important issues of physical culture lessons is how to structure it. A lesson plan is an approximate plan used to create a separate lesson. The content of the lesson helps the teacher to choose exercises wisely, to place the material correctly and to determine the load in the lesson. It is necessary to introduce new materials to each lesson and give students physical loads in moderation. The main part of physical education classes causes some nervousness in children, their pulse and breathing speed up. In order to create favorable conditions for students to switch to another type of activity, it is necessary to bring the student body to a very restrained state. The easing of exercises started at the end of the main part should end with the end of the lesson. A gradual transition to a relatively calm state is achieved by simple formations, walks, rhythmic and deep breathing exercises, and quiet games. The contents of the components of physical education lessons are reflected in the lesson notes. Lesson notes describe the purpose and task of the lesson, as well as the definition of physical exercises and physical movements. Currently, in all regions of our country, it is important to promote the importance of mass sports in human and family life, that it is the basis of physical and spiritual health, to protect young people who enter life with high hopes from harmful habits, to teach them their abilities and desires. There are important and urgent tasks to create the necessary conditions for them to realize their talents, to select talented athletes from among them, and to improve the targeted training system. Currently, it is very important to involve children in public and independent physical activities,

training them, especially to make them healthy, strong, resilient, and agile. In this textbook, the subject, main concepts, goals and tasks of physical education theory and methodology, as well as physical education tools, teaching and training methods used in physical education, a general description of physical qualities and control of their development, pedagogical control in physical education and sports classes are presented in this textbook. At each stage in the development of physical culture, the content of wealth (wealth that satisfies human needs) can be taught, used, and further developed as much as possible. Here the word is the forms of physical culture that are widespread today: gymnastics, sports, sports games, physical culture as a set of physical exercises, which is included in practical and other sections of social life and long development of activities. the content and form of physical culture gradually changed (education and training, material production and service activities, daily life and recreation, medicine) In school, in production, at home, recreational treatment led to the establishment of physical culture, etc. Achievements in sports to increase the effectiveness of physical culture in society depend on technical and other conditions (medical supplies, sports information, special sports equipment) and equipment).

Extensive scientific research in physical culture began much later than in many other areas of culture. The practical expansion of the movement of physical culture and the increasing potential of physical culture in the life of society increased the demand for scientific thinking, and at the same time, opportunities were created for its implementation in life. The restoration of various departments of the system of scientific knowledge about physical culture has not happened. Before other departments, knowledge about physical education appeared. First of all, this was due to the fact that physical education as the main form of physical culture, from the beginning of its history, formed a large part of the general social practice of education. The theory and methodology of physical education, which appeared on its basis, developed in direct connection with the science of pedagogy

and was formed much earlier as a relatively developed scientific-practical subject. The declaration of education as a priority in the field of social development of our country in the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" assigned the science of physical culture great responsibility and great tasks. A number of basic issues of the scientific theory of physical education were put forward by great scientists and public figures in our country (including Abu Ali ibn Sina, Amir Temur)). The theory and methodology of physical education was formalized as an educational subject in the teaching of higher physical culture. Among specially formed subjects, the subject directly connected with physical culture is the theory of physical education. However, it cannot reflect the whole theory of physical education, because physical culture is not manifested only in the form of physical education. Another developed subject summarizing scientific knowledge in the field of physical culture is sports theory. The rapid development of this science, especially in the last decades, was caused by the high sports results shown at the Olympic Games and in the international sports movement in general.

Modern pedagogical methodology of formation of physical culture among the students of higher education is a complex educational process, which includes the features, tasks, forms and methods of the pedagogical process of physical culture. In fact, physical culture is a view of a person's physical development based on physical qualities and abilities. In the process of human maturation, each area offers unique solutions to preserve the body's abilities, increase its activity, restore damaged functions. The development and research of the criteria of physical culture which is specific to each age group shows how important physical maturity is in human civilization today. The analysis and the experimental work carried out in the the scope of this research are aimed at shaping the physical culture of students and determining its effectiveness. This chapter is devoted to the enlighten the methodology of the pedagogical process for the development of students' physical culture. Physical culture reveals the natural tendencies of

human motor activity. Through this, the body grows depending on the laws of human physical condition and health, and realizes important abilities for life. Therefore, in the educational process, it is important to strengthen the physical culture of students and develop important skills for health. The higher education institution also conducts internships to develop physical culture skills in students through physical education classes. Today, the aim is to increase the effectiveness of this pedagogical process through new methods, interactive methods.

References:

1. Mirziyoev Sh.M. Buyuk kelajagimizni mard va olijanob xalqimiz bilan birga quramiz. –T.: O’zbekiston, 2017. – 488 b.
2. Abdukado’rov A.A., Eshnazarova M.Yu. Elektronno’e uchebniki v sisteme distantsionnogo obrazovaniya G’G’ Pedagogika jene psixologiya. – Almata, 2010. - №4. –B. 184-187.
3. Tolipov O’K. Masofali o’qitish yoki zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalardan dars jarayonida foydalanish G’G’ O’rta maxsus, kasb-hunar ta’limi tizimiga pedagogik va axborot texnologiyalarini tatbiq etish muammolari: Respublika ilmiy-amaliy konferentsiya materiallari. – Toshkent: O’MKHTRI, 2004. –B. 121.
4. Usmonxodjaev T. S. va boshqa. Talabalar va o’smirlar sporta mashg’ulotlari nazariyasi va uslubiyatlari. 2005 y. Toshkent.
5. Achilov A.M. Akramov J.A. Goncharova O.V. Bolalarning jismoniy sifatlarini tarbiyalash. 2004 y. Toshkent.